

Euscorpium

Occasional Publications in Scorpiology

**A new species of *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 from
Yunnan Province, China, with a preliminary
review of its congeners in Yunnan
(Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae)**

Victoria Tang

October 2022 — No. 360

Euscorpius

Occasional Publications in Scorpiology

EDITOR: **Victor Fet**, Marshall University, 'fet@marshall.edu'

ASSOCIATE EDITOR: **Michael E. Soleglad**, 'msoleglad@gmail.com'

TECHNICAL EDITOR: **František Kovařík**, 'kovarik.scorpio@gmail.com'

Euscorpius is the first research publication completely devoted to scorpions (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Euscorpius* takes advantage of the rapidly evolving medium of quick online publication, at the same time maintaining high research standards for the burgeoning field of scorpion science (scorpiology). *Euscorpius* is an expedient and viable medium for the publication of serious papers in scorpiology, including (but not limited to): systematics, evolution, ecology, biogeography, and general biology of scorpions. Review papers, descriptions of new taxa, faunistic surveys, lists of museum collections, and book reviews are welcome.

Derivatio Nominis

The name *Euscorpius* Thorell, 1876 refers to the most common genus of scorpions in the Mediterranean region and southern Europe (family Euscorpiidae).

Euscorpius is located at: <https://mds.marshall.edu/euscorpius/>
Archive of issues 1-270 see also at: <http://www.science.marshall.edu/fet/Euscorpius>

(Marshall University, Huntington, West Virginia 25755-2510, USA)

ICZN COMPLIANCE OF ELECTRONIC PUBLICATIONS:

Electronic (“e-only”) publications are fully compliant with ICZN (*International Code of Zoological Nomenclature*) (i.e. for the purposes of new names and new nomenclatural acts) when properly archived and registered. All *Euscorpius* issues starting from No. 156 (2013) are archived in two electronic archives:

- **Biotaxa**, <http://biotaxa.org/Euscorpius> (ICZN-approved and ZooBank-enabled)
- **Marshall Digital Scholar**, <http://mds.marshall.edu/euscorpius/>. (This website also archives all *Euscorpius* issues previously published on CD-ROMs.)

Between 2000 and 2013, ICZN *did not accept online texts* as “published work” (Article 9.8). At this time, *Euscorpius* was produced in two *identical* versions: online (*ISSN 1536-9307*) and CD-ROM (*ISSN 1536-9293*) (laser disk) in archive-quality, read-only format. Both versions had the identical date of publication, as well as identical page and figure numbers. **Only copies distributed on a CD-ROM** from *Euscorpius* in 2001-2012 represent published work in compliance with the ICZN, i.e. for the purposes of new names and new nomenclatural acts.

In September 2012, ICZN Article 8. What constitutes published work, has been amended and allowed for electronic publications, disallowing publication on optical discs. From January 2013, *Euscorpius* discontinued CD-ROM production; only online electronic version (*ISSN 1536-9307*) is published. For further details on the new ICZN amendment, see <http://www.pensoft.net/journals/zookeys/article/3944/>.

Publication date: 2 October 2022

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:EE7FEBED-036E-4888-ACE6-BCA80C1A006A>

A new species of *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 from Yunnan Province, China, with a preliminary review of its congeners in Yunnan (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae)

Victoria Tang

Zhangyang Rd. 200120, Pudong New District, Shanghai, China; email: jibril.flueqel@gmail.com

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:EE7FEBED-036E-4888-ACE6-BCA80C1A006A>

Summary

A new species of *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861, *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n., is described from Yingjiang, Yunnan Province, China, based on a single adult female. The morphology of the new species is fairly distinguishable from other congeners in Yunnan even with unaided eye; it is characterized by the following combination of characters in female: a pair of moderately robust pedipalp chelae without proximal lobes, small median ocular tubercle, short superciliary carinae, less granulated tergites, proportionally elongate metasoma and relatively short and bulbous vesicle. The coloration of the new species also differs from other congeners in Yunnan by being brownish in tergites and telson vesicle. The number of known species of *Scorpiops* from China is raised to 29 (22 endemic) and that of Yunnan is raised to 10 (9 endemic). The previously described congeners from Yunnan are also revisited, by complementing some missing data of several species, and providing new comparative data for the following species based on recently collected topotypes: *S. puerensis* (Di et al., 2010), *S. shidian* (Qi et al., 2005), *S. vachoni* (Qi et al., 2005), *S. validus* (Di et al., 2010), and *S. zhangshuyuani* (Ythier, 2019), as well as the Yunnan population of *S. kubani* (Kovařík, 2004). Finally, *Scorpiops validus* (Di et al., 2010) **stat. rev.** is restored from its synonymy with *S. vachoni* (Qi et al., 2005).

Introduction

Yunnan Province lies in the southwest of China, covering an area of 394,100 km², characterized as a mountainous, transitional terrain from the high altitude of Qinghai-Tibet Plateau in the northwest, towards the low-altitude Malaysian Peninsula in the southeast. The vast land area of Yunnan with complex landforms includes various terrestrial ecosystems and climate zones, which provide favorable habitats for different species with specific preference, thus featuring it as an enormous biodiversity hotspot. Yunnan is also one of three provinces that exhibit the highest scorpion diversity in China (11 species of 3 genera; the other two provinces are Xizang (29 species of 6 genera) and Xinjiang (7 species of 4 genera); see the checklist in Tang (2022c) and Lv & Di (2022)). A relict scorpion family, Pseudochactidae Gromov, 1998, has also been confirmed from this province with a monotypic genus, *Qianxie* Tang, 2022. The numerous karst caves in Yunnan have not been investigated thoroughly and there is a likelihood of subterranean scorpion species being found there.

Kovařík et al. (2020) revised the family Scorpiopidae Kraepelin, 1905 by investigating and evaluating extensive morphological characters, and synonymized all the genera and one subgenus (*Alloscorpis* Vachon, 1980, *Dasyscorpis*

Vachon, 1974, *Euscorpis* Vachon, 1980, *Neoscorpis* Vachon, 1980, *Plethoscorpis* Lourenço, 2017, *Vietscorpis* Lourenço & Pham, 2015, and *Alloscorpis* (*Laoscorpis*) Lourenço, 2013), which had been placed in this family (except for *Parascorpis* Banks, 1928), with the type genus, *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861. This taxonomic decision was further supported by the molecular study by Šťáhlavský et al. (2020), which revealed the genera *Alloscorpis*, *Dasyscorpis*, *Euscorpis* and *Scorpiops* s. str., to be polyphyletic. Prior to that, both *Scorpiops* and *Euscorpis* have been recorded in China. Several species in China were also synonymized (Kovařík et al., 2020): *Euscorpis karschi* Lourenço et al., 2005 with *Scorpiops novaki* (Kovařík, 2005), and *Scorpiops pococki* Zhu et al., 2005 with *Scorpiops tibetanus* Hirst, 1911. Tang (2022c) retained another two synonyms that were proposed by Kovařík et al. (2020) (*Scorpiops atomatus* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005 (syn. with *S. tibetanus*) and *Scorpiops validus* (Di et al., 2010) (syn. with *S. vachoni*)) based on a logical deduction but did not formally restore them from synonymy.

Within China, *Scorpiops* is the most speciose genus and has so far been formally recorded from four provinces: Xizang (17 species), Yunnan (9 species), Xinjiang (1 species), and Hubei (1 species). Anecdotal observations of at least one

Figures 1–3: **Figure 1.** Measurement of pedipalp chela length (red line) and width (yellow line). The figure shows dorsal aspect of right pedipalp chela of *Scorpions tongtongi* sp. n., female holotype, under UV light. **Figure 2.** Carapace of *S. jendeki*, under UV light; photo not stacked. **Figure 3.** Tergites of *S. jendeki*, under UV light.

unidentified species encountered by the local people were reported from Chongqing Province (the relationship between this species and the one from Hubei is unclear); the species of this genus in the central region await further investigation. In Xizang Province, the *Scorpiops* species are essentially concentrated in the south, while in Yunnan Province, they are distributed along the national border in the southwest (see the map in Tang (2022c) and Lv & Di (2022)). Previously, nine species have been recorded from Yunnan; eight of them are endemic to China (the type locality of *S. kubani* (Kovařík, 2004) is in Laos).

The present study describes the ninth endemic *Scorpiops* species from Yingjiang County, Dehong Prefecture, Yunnan Province, and the number of known scorpion species in China is raised to 29. The new species, *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n., is based on a single adult female as no other individuals were collected in the vicinity of the type locality. However, the new species is very distinct from any other known species in Yunnan (especially those distributed in proximity) and is located in an area that is disjunct from all the congeners in adjacent countries. *S. tongtongi* sp. n. is characterized by a pair of moderately robust pedipalp chelae without proximal lobes, small median ocular tubercle and short superciliary carinae in the female. These characters are very prominent without the necessity of conducting morphometric measurement. The coloration of the new species also differs from other congeners in Yunnan by being brownish on tergites and telson vesicle.

Finally, brief comments are also made upon the *Scorpiops* species in Yunnan, focused on the morphological identification of these species, as well as the applicability of the diagnostic characters used in the previous papers. New morphological data are provided for *S. puerensis*, *S. shidian*, *S. vachoni*, *S. validus* and *S. zhangshuyuani* based on recently collected topotypes, and the *S. kubani* population in Yunnan. Based on this new information, *S. validus* is hereby restored from its synonymy with *S. vachoni*.

Methods, Materials & Abbreviations

Nomenclature and measurements follow Stahnke (1971), Soleglad & Sissom (2001), Kovařík (2009), and Kovařík & Ojanguren Affilastro (2013), except for trichobothriotaxy (Vachon, 1974), sternum (Soleglad & Fet, 2003a) and chelicerae (Soleglad & Fet, 2003b). To clarify, the total length is summed with data measured from carapace (from the anterior margin of the anterolateral lobes flanking the anterior medial notch), each tergite (from the midpoint of pretergite) and metasomal segment, and telson. Measurement of length and width of the pedipalp chela is shown in Fig. 1 and defined as follows: (1) length, the linear distance from the distal tip of fixed finger to the proximal end of the digital carina; (2) width, the maximum linear distance between the base line of the dorsal internal carina and the external carina (i.e., excluding granules that could be variable in depth) from dorsal aspect (by adjusting the chela and making the dorsal surface parallel to a horizontal foam board). In some individuals, adjacent pectinal

teeth may be fused, and in such a case that pectinal tooth was counted twice. Maturity-dependent characters (e.g., total length, lobe development and L/W ratio) were all exclusively recorded for adults, while other discrete, ontogenetically invariant characters (e.g., pectinal tooth count, number of trichobothria and finger dentition) were enumerated for all specimens (unless the relevant structure is damaged, e.g., tip of the finger). The collector of the topotypes of *S. vachoni* intended to keep the juveniles alive and retain them in his own collection, thus only pectinal teeth and ventral trichobothria of pedipalp patella were enumerated (juveniles are more agile and not convenient to be examined alive).

The holotype female of the new species and the topotypes of several congeners (and the Yunnan population of *S. kubani*) were received from Yunnan collectors, and photos were taken of their *in vivo* habitus under captive conditions if they arrived as living specimens (some of the specimens died during the trip due to the high temperature, e.g., all the *S. kubani*). The holotype and two pairs of each congener (except for *S. zhangshuyuani*) were euthanized in a freezer, prior to the fixation in 99% ethanol. All the remaining topotypes (and *S. kubani*) were either kept in 75% ethanol or kept alive (essentially the females) for breeding future generations of offspring. Examination of live specimens was conducted after immersing the scorpion under water for a few minutes, causing hypoxia. In order to implement the reanalysis in a transparent and open manner, photographs of pedipalp chelae and pectines of all the adult topotypes (and *S. kubani*) are provided here. Most photos were taken under the UV light since all the involved species were basically darkly pigmented without any obvious color pattern. Some illustrations (Figs. 6–32) were assembled by merging images acquired from different planes of focus using the software Zerenestacker 1.04 (Zerene Systems LLC, Washington, USA).

Sex determination was based on the presence/absence of genital papillae (present in males), while maturity was primarily based on the size. Some of the females examined were mature as can be told from the presence of embryos which can be seen in ventral profile (these females were also very large and the overall ratio, especially that of the pedipalp chelae, suggested they were indeed mature). If a female individual was smaller than average with noticeably more slender pedipalps, it was dissected to ascertain the presence/absence of embryos. Several males were conspicuously smaller to the largest males and they were dissected to determine the presence/absence of hemispermatophores, which are proof of sexual maturity, even if the sexually dimorphic proximal lobe on the dorsal edge of movable finger was very pronounced.

In this study, these three species are grouped together based on the previous morphological data and defined as the “*Scorpiops vachoni* complex” for brevity (*S. puerensis* (Di, Wu, Cao, Xiao & Li, 2010), *S. vachoni* (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005) and *S. validus* (Di, Cao, Wu & Li, 2010) (note that Kovařík et al. (2020) synonymized *S. validus* with *S. vachoni*)): (1) coloration essentially brownish black; (2) proximal lobe of the pedipalp movable finger pronounced in

Figures 4–5. *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n., female holotype, dorsal (4) and ventral (5) views, under white light. Scale bar = 10 mm.

both sexes with females being weaker; (3) chela moderately elongate (between *S. jendeki* and *S. shidian*; or, chela L/W ratio 2.6–3.2); (4) number of ventral and external patellar trichobothria ranges from 8–11 and 17–18, respectively; (5) PTC 6–8; (6) trichobothrium Eb_3 located in distal half of manus between *Dt* and *Est*; (7) pectines with 3 marginal and 1–5 middle lamellae present.

Specimen Depository: VT (Personal collection of Victoria Tang, Pudong New District, Shanghai, China).

Morphometrics: D, depth; L, length; W, width; nVt, number of ventral trichobothria; nEt, number of external trichobothria; PTC, pectinal tooth count.

Movable finger dentition: ID, inner denticles; IAD, inner accessory denticles; MD, median denticles; OD, outer denticles. In some individuals, there may be few extra denticles

between MD and IAD, and they were not enumerated. See Fig. 268 for example.

Erratum. In the second map provided in Tang (2022c: 4, fig 2) which illustrated the distribution of parvorder Iurida in China, the author referred to the distributional map of *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 in Kovařík et al. (2020: 127, fig 799). The locality of *Scorpiops puerensis* (Di, Wu, Cao, Xiao & Li, 2010) was approximated as the location of Puer City (Yunnan) in both papers as no coordinates were provided in the original description of this species. However, after checking other previous papers that had provided a distributional map, the type locality of this species seems to be far away from the city (e.g., Di et al. (2011b): 30, fig 123). A more accurate map is given in the present study.

Dimensions (mm)		<i>S. tongtongi</i> sp. n. ♀ HT
Carapace	L / W	6.7 / 6.9
Mesosoma	L	12.4
Tergite VII	L / W	2.6 / 5.5
Metasoma + telson	L	22.8
Segment I	L / W / D	2.3 / 2.6 / 2.2
Segment II	L / W / D	2.6 / 2.2 / 2.1
Segment III	L / W / D	2.7 / 2.1 / 2.1
Segment IV	L / W / D	3.3 / 2.0 / 2.1
Segment V	L / W / D	5.7 / 2.0 / 1.9
Telson	L / W / D	6.2 / 2.0 / 2.2
Pedipalp	L	26.1
Femur	L / W	5.7 / 2.2
Patella	L / W	5.6 / 2.7
Chela	L	12.0
Manus	L / W / D	7.8 / 4.2 / 3.2
Fixed Finger	L	4.2
Movable finger	L	6.6
Total	L	41.9
Pectine Teeth number	L / R	6 / 6

Table 1. Measurements of *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n. female holotype. Abbreviations: length (L), width (W, in carapace it corresponds to posterior width), depth (D).

Systematics

Family Scorpiopidae Kraepelin, 1905 Genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861

Scorpiops tongtongi sp. n. (Figures 1, 4–34, Table 1)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:7A317530-A04C-48E8-8061-B99958D3DED6>

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE REPOSITORY. **China**, Yunnan Province, Dehong Prefecture, Yingjiang County, 24°37'39"N 97°38'27"E, 1451 m a. s. l; VT.

TYPE MATERIAL. **China**, Yunnan Province, Dehong Prefecture, Yingjiang County, 24°37'39"N 97°38'27"E, 1451 m a. s. l, 4 July 2022, 1♀ (holotype), leg. Tongtong; VT.

COMPARATIVE MATERIAL (VT). *Scorpiops jendeki* Kovařík, 2000, **China**, Yunnan Province, Baoshan City, 5♀; *Scorpiops kubani* (Kovařík, 2004), **China**, Yunnan Province, Xishuangbanna Prefecture, Menghai County, Menghai Town, 21°58'18"N 100°27'44"E, 1193 m a. s. l, 21 July 2022, 7♂8♀, leg. Hang Qiu; *Scorpiops puerensis* (Di, Wu, Cao, Xiao & Li, 2010), **China**, Yunnan Province, Puer City, Lancang

Lahu Autonomous County, Zha Ga Liang Zi, 22°32'06"N 99°55'39"E, 1137 m a. s. l, 18 July 2022, 5♂5♀, leg. Jinping He; *Scorpiops shidian* (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005), **China**, Yunnan Province, Baoshan City, Shidian County, Jin Tang Ba (Jintang dam), 24°33'13"N 99°02'57"E, 816 m a. s. l, June (whole month) 2022, 4♂7♀ 2♂1♀juv., leg. Guohao Yang; *Scorpiops vachoni* (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005), **China**, Yunnan Province, Xishuangbanna Prefecture, Mengla County, Bujiao Township, 21°29'89"N 101°32'47"E, 793 m a. s. l, 26 August 2022, 5♂3♀ 11♂2♀juv., leg. Qingquan Jia; *Scorpiops validus* (Di, Cao, Wu & Li, 2010), **China**, Yunnan Province, Honghe Hani and Yi Autonomous Prefecture, Honghe County, Mengzi City, 23°19'07"N 103°19'42"E, 1530 m a. s. l, 6 August 2022, 5♂5♀1♀juv.; *Scorpiops zhangshuyuan* (Ythier, 2019), **China**, Yunnan Province, Dehong Prefecture, Yingjiang County, 24°37'39"N 97°34'47"E, 1030 m a. s. l, 5–6 July 2022, 1♂1♀, leg. Tongtong; *Scorpiops* sp., **China**, Yunnan Province, Xishuangbanna Prefecture, Jinghong City, Mt. Jinuo, 24°34'15"N 100°59'33"E, 1039 m a. s. l., 9 July 2022, 1♂, leg. Qingquan Jia.

ETYMOLOGY. The specific epithet is named in honor of my friend and the collector of the type specimen, Tongtong (通通), who is an enthusiastic nature observer and collector in Yunnan, and has been recording numerous *Scorpiops* species in China for years. He was also one of the providers of the locality of *Qianxie solegladi* Tang, 2022.

Chinese equivalent. 通氏类蝎 (roughly as “Tongtong’s resemblant scorpion” in English; see Tang (2022a) for the rules of designation).

DIAGNOSIS (based on holotype female). Total length 41.9 mm. Base color uniformly reddish brown to brownish black, telson and parts of legs brown to brownish yellow. Pectinal teeth number 6–6; fulcra present; pectines form one compact unit with an incomplete furrow between areas where marginal and middle lamellae are usually delimited. Patella of pedipalp with 17 external and 7 ventral trichobothria. Chela with 4 *V* series trichobothria located on the ventral surface. Chelal trichobothrium *Eb*₃ located in middle of manus between trichobothria *Dt* and *Est*. Dorsal edge of movable fingers of pedipalps not undulate (no proximal lobe present). Chela length to width ratio 2.85. Pedipalp movable finger with ca. 45–50 IAD, which have the same size as MD (ca. 85–90 in number) and create a second row of denticles; there are also 4 ID and 11 OD present. Tarsomere II of leg III with 5–6 stout median ventral spinules in a single row, and two pairs of flanking setae. Metasoma I with 10 carinae, II–IV with 8 carinae, V with 7 carinae. Telson relatively short and bulbous, and densely covered with fine granules, length to depth ratio 2.8; annular ring developed (circumference constricted at the vesicle/aculeus juncture).

DESCRIPTION. Photos of the specimen in Figs. 4–5, 33–34 were taken under white light (specimen *in vivo* habitus is shown in Figs. 33–34). Photos of the specimen in Figs. 1, 6–32 were

Figures 6–9. *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n., female holotype, carapace (6), tergites I–VII (7), sternopectinal region (8) and sternites (9), under UV light.

Figures 10–11. *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n., female holotype, respiratory spiracle (10) and pectines (11), under UV light.

Figures 12–24. *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n., female holotype, pedipalp chela dorsal (12), external (13) and ventral (14) views, patella dorsal (15), external (16) and ventral (17) views, femur and trochanter dorsal (18), external (19) and ventral (20) views, left movable finger (21), right movable finger (22), and dorsal (23) and ventral (24) views of chelicera. The trichobothrial pattern is indicated in Figures 12–17 and finger dentation is captioned in Figures 21–22 (IAD = yellow, MD = green, ID = blue, OD = red). Abbr.: digital (d), subdigital (sd), dorsal secondary (ds), dorsal marginal (dm), dorsal internal (di), intermedian (im), ventrointernal (vi), ventromedian (vm), ventroexternal (ve) and external secondary (es) carinae; prodorsal (pd), retrodorsal (rd), retromedian (rm), retroventral (rv), proventral (pv), promedian (pm) carinae and spiniform apophysis (sa).

Figures 25–32: *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n., female holotype, under UV light. Figures 25–27. Metasoma and telson, dorsal (25), lateral (26) and ventral (27) views. Figure 28. Telson lateral view. Figures 29–32. Left legs I–IV, retrolateral view. Abbr.: dorsosubmedian (dsm), dorsolateral (dl), median lateral (ml), ventrolateral (vl), ventrosubmedian (vsm) and ventromedian (vm) carinae.

taken under UV light so as to depict cuticular morphosculture (granulation and carinae). Morphometric data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Coloration (*in vivo*) (Figs. 33–34). Base color uniformly reddish brown to brownish black. Color darker on pedipalps, with the strongest carinae and pedipalp finger even darker, and on ca. 3/4 area of carapace, remaining 1/4 area in posterior region lighter. Mesosoma essentially reddish brown, with middle line and posterior margin of each tergite darker (except for VII); granules darker. Metasoma relatively darker than that of mesosoma, especially along carinae. Telson tawny, becoming lighter towards the vesicle/aculeus juncture and abruptly darkened at the aculeus, eventually turning black. Legs variegated with different degrees of brown, becoming brownish yellow distally towards telotarsi. Chelicerae brownish, becoming darker at anterior margin of manus and on both fingers. Ventral coloration of prosoma light brown; posterior area of sternum brownish yellow. Genital operculum, pectines and sternites yellowish, with pectinal teeth slightly darker; color becoming darker towards sternite VII; areas of book lungs anterior to each respiratory spiracle light yellow.

Prosoma and mesosoma (Figs. 6–11, 23–24). *Prosoma*: Carapace with 3 pairs of lateral eyes of which two are larger and one is smaller. Superciliary carinae of the median ocelli smooth, short and compact, closely spaced. Median dorsal part the carapace (ca. half of total area) planar, from anterior to posterior margins; lateral surfaces slanting downwards. Lateral surfaces with a pair of shallow central lateral sulci and posterior lateral sulci. Entire carapace sparsely covered with small to moderate size granules; distinct carinae absent (only indicated along the margins of the dorsal plane). Anterior margin of carapace with a prominent median notch (emargination) leading to a deep, wide, smooth anteromedian sulcus. Circumocular sulcus is connected with anteromedian sulcus anteriorly, and with posteromedian sulcus posteriorly. Larger granules concentrated at edges flanking anteromedian sulcus, and above and posterior to lateral ocelli. Chelicerae with dorsal surface smooth and ventral surface setose; macrosetae localized on fixed finger. Dorsal distal, ventral distal and distal denticles of cheliceral fingers very long. *Mesosoma*: tergites sparsely covered with large granules close to posterior margins, becoming progressively denser towards lateral sides, with one median carina indicated (conspicuous on tergites IV, V and VI, and deconstructed into random granules on VII). Tergite VII is pentacarinata. Sternites smooth with sparse macrosetae, fluorescent microsetae and two parallel furrows furnished with lattice microstructure (Fig. 10, arrow) (except sternite VII which has four granulate carinae); respiratory spiracles suboval. Pectines form one compact unit with incomplete furrow between areas where marginal and middle lamellae are usually delimited; pectine teeth number 6; sensory area with small coverage at distal margin of each pectinal tooth, facing inwardly; fulcra present; fluorescent microsetae stout.

Metasoma and telson (Figs. 25–28). Metasoma sparsely hirsute and granulated; carinae with relatively large granules.

Metasomal segment I with 10 carinae, II–IV with 8 carinae, and V with 7 carinae. Median lateral carina of metasoma II–IV incomplete, presented by several posterior granules. Granules relatively smaller and thinner on the dorsosubmedian (I–IV), median lateral (V) and dorsolateral (V) carinae, larger and rounded on dorsolateral (I–IV), median lateral (I), ventrolateral (I–III) and ventrosubmedian (I–III) carinae. Granules become conspicuously sharper on ventrolateral (IV–V), ventrosubmedian (IV) and ventromedian carinae (V). Anal arch armed with sharp granules. Telson relatively short and bulbous for the genus, dorsomedian surface smooth, dorsolateral, lateral and ventral surfaces with dense fine granulation, granules coarser on ventral surface, annular ring developed. Vesicle sparsely covered with fluorescent microsetae and few macrosetae, with a pair of smooth, shallow sulci on lateral surfaces.

Pedipalps (Figs. 12–24). Pedipalps very sparsely hirsute. Patella with 17 external (4 *et*, 4 *est*, 2 *em*, 2 *esb*, 5 *eb*) and 7 ventral trichobothria. Chela with 4 *V* series trichobothria located on ventral surface. Chelal trichobothrium *Eb*₃ located in middle of manus between trichobothria *Dt* and *Est*. Femur and patella granulated. Intercarinal surfaces scattered with small to moderate granules. Femur with 6 granulate carinae; promedian carina incomplete, composed of several granules; retroventral carina incomplete, reduced to small granules; granules larger on prodorsal, retrodorsal, retromedian and proventral carinae. Patella with 5 granulate carinae, composed of large granules; retrodorsal carina granular to costate-granular; prolateral surface with three small spiniform apophyses. Manus dorsally with fine, rounded granules; largest granules constitute digital, dorsal marginal and ventromedian carinae; moderate size granules present on interomedian carina; subdigital, dorsal secondary, dorsal internal, ventrointernal, ventroexternal, and external secondary carinae incomplete or obsolete, gradually weakening to dispersed granules. Movable fingers with ca. 45–50 IAD, which have the same size as MD (ca. 80–90 in number) and form a second row, but with no clear separation between the two rows proximally; 4 ID and 11 OD also present.

Legs (Figs. 29–32). Tibia and tarsomeres of legs with several macrosetae and fluorescent microsetae not arranged into bristle combs on dorsal surfaces, but with rows of spinules on dorsolateral surfaces and on legs I–II also on ventrolateral surfaces (spinules on ventrolateral surfaces of legs I–II denser and longer, forming conspicuous rows). Tarsomere II of legs I–IV with row of 5–6 short, stout median ventral spinules, and two pairs of flanking setae. Femur with 3–4 and patella 4–5 carinae; both femur and patella finely granulated, with sparse setae.

Variation. Only one adult female has been collected, thus no intraspecific variation can be documented.

Measurements. See Tables 1 and 2.

AFFINITIES. The new species can be readily distinguished from three closely distributed congeners in Yunnan by easily visible features, without microscopic examination, as follows

Figures 33–34: *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n., in vivo habitus. Figure 33. Female holotype. Figure 34. Comparison between *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n. (left) and *Scorpiops jendeki*, both are females.

Figures 35–39: Presumed topotypes of *Scorpiops puerensis* (35), *S. shidian* (36), *S. vachoni* (37), *S. validus* (38) and *S. zhangshuyuanii* (39) *in vivo* habitus.

Figures 40–60: Pedipalp chela and pectines of males of *S. kubani*, under UV light. **Figure 40–53.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal (40–46) and dorsoexternal (47–53). **Figure 54–60.** Pectines.

(in adult females): (1) from *S. zhangshuyuani*, it can be simply distinguished by a much more robust pedipalp chela (cf. Ythier, 2019: 191, figs 1–2; 194, figs 9–10; Fig. 222) and a smaller size; (2) from *S. shidian*, it can be distinguished also by a much more robust pedipalp (cf. Di et al., 2011b: 16, figs 52–53; 17, figs 58–61; Figs. 36, 134–147); (3) from *S. jendeki*, it can be distinguished by more elongate pedipalps, less granulated tergites and more quadrate carapace (vs. more

trapezoidal carapace of *S. jendeki*) (Figs. 2–3, 34; and a larger size). Morphologically, the new species is most similar to four congeners in Yunnan, which are all characterized by a relatively robust pedipalp chela: *S. kubani*, *S. puerensis*, *S. vachoni* and *S. validus*. However, it can be distinguished from those species as follows: (1) movable finger without proximal lobe (not undulate); (2) pedipalp chela more robust (see Tables 2 and 3); (3) dorsal surface of pedipalp chela manus flatter

and smoother (granules do not form a reticulate pattern); (4) median ocular tubercle less elevated; (5) carapace sulci wider and shallower; (6) pedipalp patella internal apophysis smaller; (7) granules on tergites larger but less dense; (8) granules on metasomal carinae and ventral surface of vesicle stronger. The other two congeners in Yunnan, *S. xui* and *S. yangi*, are both characterized by a slender pedipalp chela (Sun & Zhu, 2010: 66, fig. 14; Zhu et al., 2007: 24, figs 19–22), similar to that of *S. shidian*. Furthermore, the new species can be distinguished from all the congeners in Yunnan (except for *S. jendeki*) by the weakly developed median ocular tubercle and superciliary carinae, a less carved and smoother carapace, less granulated tergites, a proportionally longer metasoma and a more bulbous vesicle. Beyond Yunnan, the new species is closest geographically to *S. beccaloniae* (Kovařík, 2005) from Mali Hka Valley, Kachin Hills, Myanmar, which was described based on a single male specimen. Nevertheless, the new species can be distinguished from *S. beccaloniae* by a sex-independent character: ventral patellar trichobothria number 7 (vs. 12); no known species of *Scorpiops* shows strong sexual dimorphism in this number, and the greatest numerical disparity (4–6) is only presented in several species with markedly elongated pedipalps (e.g., 15–21 in *S. anthracinus* Simon, 1887). Furthermore, the spiniform apophysis on the pedipalp patella is stronger in *S. beccaloniae*, a character that does not show sexual dimorphism in this genus. The carinae on the pedipalp chelae of *S. beccaloniae* are formed by largely spaced granules of moderate to small size and the dorsal surface is covered by less granules; the telson is also less granulated in *S. beccaloniae* (F. Kovařík, pers. comm.). The chela MD counts of the two species are very different (ca. 80–90 vs. ca. 65), although there could be a substantial range of variation (see below). Pectinal morphology is also different (pectines with 3 marginal and 1–5 middle lamellae in *S. beccaloniae*; but see below for further comments). The position of trichobothrium Eb_3 is different, but there could be intraspecific variation (cf. Kovařík et al., 2020: 128–129, table 9). Other characters are similar: (1) external patellar trichobothria number 17 (vs. 18, normal variation range); (2) IAD both ca. 50; (3) ID both 4; (4) OD 11 (vs. 12–13, normal variation range). Sexual dimorphism may be presented in the following characters: (1) PTC 6 (vs. 8–9, normal sexually dimorphic range); (2) finger proximal lobe absent (vs. prominent); (3) telson vesicle bulbous (vs. elongate; or L/D ratio 2.8 vs. 3.4). Additionally, the new species is geographically isolated from *S. beccaloniae* by the Irrawaddy River and Kachin Hills.

DISTRIBUTION (Figs. 274). Known only from the type locality (Yingjiang, Dehong, Yunnan), which closely borders the Kachin State of Myanmar. This species was found in close proximity to the type locality of *Scorpiops zhangshuyuani* (Tongbiguan Township, Yingjiang, Dehong, Yunnan). According to the distributional map given in Kovařík et al. (2020: 127, fig 799), no other congeners have been recorded nearby in Myanmar. The most closely distributed species is *S. beccaloniae* (Kovařík, 2005) in the north, which has been discussed above.

ECOLOGY. Yingjiang County is a mountainous region with several alluvial plains (elevations vary from 210 to 3404 m), characterized by the subtropical monsoon climate and the annual temperature ranges from 16 to 28°C. The holotype female was found under a stone next to a drainage ditch near the mountain forest while it was extending its pedipalps outwards. No other individuals were found in the vicinity. Several topotypes of *Scorpiops zhangshuyuani* were found approximately six kilometers away. In Yunnan, the new species is found most closely to three congeners: *S. jendeki*, *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuani*. According to the collector, *S. jendeki* is often found in the decaying wood, while *S. zhangshuyuani* is found in crevices of soil slopes.

CONSERVATION STATUS. As mentioned in Tang (2022b), no species of *Scorpiops* is protected in China and many Tibetan species have rarely been encountered after their initial description. In Xizang, two species seem to be the most common: *Scorpiops tibetanus* Hirst, 1911 and *S. luridus* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005. In Yunnan, two groups of *Scorpiops* are heavily collected and sold online. The first group includes only one species, *S. jendeki* Kovařík, 2000, which is a very small species with short pedipalps. This species has been arbitrarily misidentified as *Chaerilus variegatus* Simon, 1877 (a species that only occurs in Indonesia) since 2017, by a self-righteous amateur (柳丝_Cornelius13) with zero scientific rationale provided, which circulated erroneous identifications by various vendors and successively, exacerbated by the breeders, also unfamiliar with scorpiology. The irresponsible identification, as is on full display by that amateur, will only pose unnecessary, extra obstacles against the protection of these animals and engender additional efforts for others to scotch such rumors in a country with scorpions known only by few people. Numerous species may be included in the second group, and all are characterized by a larger size and elongate pedipalps. Accurate localities of these specimens are not recorded in the pet trade, and many vendors mix together scorpions from different localities, which impedes the identification of these species. At least three species are included: *S. puerensis*, “*S. vachoni*” (most specimens are sold in the pet trade under this name, although their accuracy of identification is questionable) and *S. validus*. Besides, *S. kubani* and *S. shidian* are another two species that may be sold in the pet trade, and at least they have been collected by some amateurs. Unlike *Olivierus martensii* (Karsch, 1879) and *Mesobuthus thersites* (C. L. Koch, 1839), the targeted hunting of these *Scorpiops* species is not primarily for the purposes of medicine, food or liquor, but for pet keeping (although some collectors in Yunnan sell them as ingredients added to the medicinal herbs). Under captive conditions, these scorpions are seldom observed to perform courtship and many die from either cannibalism or physiological stress caused by inappropriate humidity and temperature. Instead, most captive newborns come from parturition of collected females that are already gravid. The captive breeding of these scorpions is not as mature as that of many of arid-adapted species imported from other countries (e.g., *Androctonus* spp., *Parabuthus* spp., etc.).

Figures 61–85: *S. kubani*, under UV light. Figures 61–76. Pedipalp chela in dorsal (61–68) and dorsoexternal (69–76) views of females. Figures 77–84. Pectines of females. Figure 85. Right pedipalp movable finger of male showing an abnormal, intricate denticle arrangement at distal part (data not recorded).

Figures 86–91. *S. kubani*, comparison between three males (86–88) and three females (89–91).

Figures 92–106: Pedipalp chela and pectines of males of *S. puerensis*, under UV light. **Figures 92–101.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal (92–96) and dorsoexternal (97–101) views. **Figures 102–106.** Pectines.

Figures 107–121: Pedipalp chela and pectines of females of *S. puerensis*, under UV light. **Figures 107–116.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal (107–111 and dorsoexternal (112–116) views. **Figures 117–121.** Pectines.

Furthermore, many individuals do not survive in environments maintained by vendors. Keeping scorpion as pets does have a benefit in counteracting negative stereotypes of the public and promoting education and knowledge about these animals if done ethically. Yet, many of the individuals die unnecessarily

and few people research the correct arachnoculture techniques appropriate for each species. The current status of their natural population has not been investigated and assessed; however, it is crucial to curb excessive collecting and protect their natural habitats.

Figures 122–133: Pedipalp chela and pectines of males of *S. shidian*, under UV light. **Figures 122–129.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal (122–125) and dorsoexternal (126–129) views. **Figures 130–133.** Pectines.

Figures 134–157: *S. shidian*, under UV light. **Figures 134–147.** Pedipalp chela of females in dorsal (134–140) and dorsoexternal (141–147) views. **Figures 148–154.** Pectines of females. **Figures 155–157.** Juveniles, pectines only, image blurred under white light; two males (155–156) and a female (157).

Comments on the *Scorpiops* species in Yunnan and the previous morphological descriptions

Hitherto, 10 species of *Scorpiops* have been recorded in Yunnan: *S. jendeki* Kovařík, 2000 from Baoshan City, *S. kubani* (Kovařík, 2004) from Menghai County, *S. puerensis* (Di, Wu, Cao, Xiao & Li, 2010) from Puer City, *S. shidian* (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005) from Shidian County, *S. vachoni* (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005) from Mengla County, *S. validus* (Di, Cao, Wu & Li, 2010) from Honghe Prefecture, *S. xui* (Sun & Zhu, 2010) from Menglian County, *S. yangi* (Zhu, Zhang & Lourenço, 2007) from Maguan County, and *S. zhangshuyuani* (Ythier, 2019) and *S. tongtongi* sp. n. from Yingjiang County. Most of these species are of medium to large body size with a pair of elongate pedipalps, except for *S. jendeki*.

All the diagnostic characters applied in the original papers as well as those in the revisions are arranged in Table 2 (mainly adapted from Kovařík et al., 2020: 128–129, table 9; except for coloration, which is subjective and is not intrinsic if it was based on long-preserved specimens). Kovařík et al. (2020) considered pectinal fulcra to be absent in *S. puerensis* and *S. validus* (as *S. vachoni*), but these structures were illustrated in their original descriptions (Di et al., 2010b: 56, figs 12, 14; Di et al., 2010a: 16, figs 9–10). As for *S. vachoni*, no fulcra were depicted in Qi et al. (2005: 21, figs 73–74), although one cannot be sure whether this species had been correctly illustrated. Therefore, the table in the present study does not entirely follow Kovařík et al. (2020). Additional qualitative descriptors such as surface granulations and shape of the pedipalp chela are not considered. For example, *S. vachoni* was consistently distinguished from *S. kubani*, *S. puerensis* and *S. validus* having rounded, rather than dorsoventrally flattened pedipalp chelae (except in Kovařík et al., 2020). This character can be quantified in terms of a ratio, the maximal depth/minimal depth ratio of the chela manus. However, photographs of the types of these four species are unavailable for comparison. The original description of *S. vachoni* failed to properly document the morphometric values and no redescription based on the holotype of this species has ever been provided. One useful qualitative species-level diagnostic character for *Scorpiops* is the proximal lobe on the dorsal edge of the pedipalp movable finger. Pedipalp fingers with this lobe have been variously described as “scalloped”, “curved”, “flexed” or “undulate” in the previous papers but could be misinterpreted as the degree of inward curvature of both fingers seen in dorsal view. The proximal lobe on the movable finger provides a bivariate character including two parameters, depth and length. The depth of the lobe is a vertical dimension indicating how far has the lobe risen from the dorsal edge, while the length is a horizontal dimension expressing the span the lobe covered thereon. Correspondingly, a notch occurs on the ventral edge of the fixed finger, and therefore can be quantified by “depth” (of the incision) and “length”. Some species of *Scorpiops* exhibit a highly elevated lobe in adult males (e.g., Kovařík et al., 2020: 7, fig. 14), while that of the others is simply wide (e.g., Kovařík et al., 2020: 7, fig.

16). Relative ratios of these characters can be utilized for interspecific comparative analysis. For example, the depth of the lobe can be compared with the depth of the movable finger at the same axis, while its length can be compared with the linear length of the dorsal edge.

Most of the diagnostic characters used to distinguish species in *Scorpiops* are quantitative, such as pedipalp L/W ratio, number of external and ventral trichobothria on pedipalp patella, PTC and L/D ratio of telson. Among these, some of the characters show substantial overlap between species. Within the Yunnan *Scorpiops*, the number of external trichobothria on the pedipalp patella ranges from 17 to 19. Excluding *S. jendeki* (which is the most distinct species of all these congeners), the number of ventral trichobothria on the pedipalp patella usually ranges from 9 to 11 (but the minimal and the maximal counts are recorded in two species: 8 in *S. validus* and 12 in *S. shidian*) and the PTC usually ranges from 6 to 8 (*S. yangi* has been recorded with the lowest count of 5). Some of the characters cannot be ascertained as no photos have been provided (artificial illustrations could be wrong), such as the presence/absence of pectinal fulcra, as well as the chela shape as aforementioned. The number of “basal teeth” on the ventral edge of the cheliceral movable finger was used as a diagnostic character by some Chinese authors. For example, in the original description of *S. yangi*, the authors mentioned that their new species possesses 5 “basal teeth” while in *S. shidian* and *S. vachoni*, the number is higher (Zhu et al., 2007: 20; 6–7 in *S. shidian* (Di et al., 2011a), unknown in *S. vachoni*). Apparently, those authors misunderstood the definition of cheliceral dentition. As defined by Soleglad and Fet (2003), the “basal tooth (or denticle)” is included in the dorsal series of denticles, while the ventral series only includes the ventral distal denticle and the ventral accessory denticle. As a result, this character is disregarded in the present study, and also due to the fact that this character has not been thoroughly described in all the species. Re-examination of these species is required to determine the diagnostic applicability of this character.

Values of length and width ratios may be sensitive to small variations in orientation angles of segments during measurement. The cited values are only referential unless all measurements are repeated under strictly controlled conditions by the same observer. The L/W ratio of the pedipalp chela is always an important morphometric character in differentiating *Scorpiops* species, however, it can be inconsistent among different authors. For example, the L/W ratio of *S. shidian* provided in Di et al. (2011a: 11, table 2) ranges from 3.2 to 3.5, but in Kovařík et al. (2020: 128, table 9), it was recorded as 3.3–3.7. Similarly, the lowest value for *S. kubani* is given as 2.7 in Di et al. (2011a: 11, table 2) but as 3.1 in Kovařík et al. (2020: 128, table 9). Additionally, the morphometric value for *S. vachoni* provided in the original description is erroneous, but from the illustration it seemed to be similar to that of *S. puerensis*. It is possible that the authors of *S. vachoni* recorded the morphometrics for “chela manus”, rather than “chela”: “...Measurements (male holotype/female paratype)...chela length, 8.23/6.38, width, 5.61/3.32...” (Qi, Zhu & Lourenço,

Figures 158–172: Pedipalp chela and pectines of males of *S. vachoni*, under UV light. **Figures 158–167.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal (158–162) and dorsoexternal (163–167) views. **Figures 168–172.** Pectines.

2005: 18). To avoid such ambiguity, the measurement method applied for pedipalp chela length and width in this study is clarified (Fig. 1). Three groups can be defined to include all

the Yunnan species: (1) very short and stout chela (*S. jendeki*); (2) relatively elongate and slender chela (*S. shidian*, *S. xui*, *S. yangi* and *S. zhangshuyuani*); (3) relatively elongate but

Figures 173–183: *S. vachoni*, under UV light. **Figures 173–178.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal 173–175 and dorsoexternal 176–178 views of females. **Figures 179–181.** Pectines of females. **Figure 182.** Left pedipalp movable finger of a male showing disordered dentation which were not enumerated. **Figure 183.** Left pedipalp patella of a juvenile male, showing 8 ventral trichobothria.

Figures 184–185: Comparison between two males *S. vachoni*.

robust chela (*S. kubani*, *S. puerensis*, *S. vachoni*, *S. validus* and *S. tongtongi* sp. n.). Kovařík et al. (2020) were the first to document the L/D ratio of the telson, but the prospect of this application in *Scorpiops* diagnosis remains unclear as the authors did not discuss this character in detail.

Kovařík et al. (2020) conducted a major reassessment of the genus-group taxa in Scorpiopidae. Although most of the characters they studied were aimed at generic revision, some of them were included in the species-keys table (Kovařík et al., 2020: 128–129, table 9) and these were never emphasized in the previous studies. The first character is the relative position of trichobothrium Eb_3 on the pedipalp chela manus. Five combinations were defined and most of the Yunnan species fell into combination A (Eb_3 located in distal half of manus between *Dt* and *Est*): *S. puerensis*, *S. shidian*, *S. vachoni* (including *S. validus*), *S. xui*, *S. yangi*, and *S. zhangshuyuani*. On the other hand, *S. jendeki* fell into combination D (Eb_3 located in proximal

half of manus between *Dt* and *Db*) and *S. kubani* fell into combination C (Eb_3 located in middle of manus between *Dt* and *Est*). Furthermore, combination C also is found in *S. zhangshuyuani*. As suggested by the authors, the placement and number of trichobothria on the pedipalps (including the accessory ones) are correlated with the morphological adaptation, and in the lithophilic species, which usually exhibit elongate appendages, there are more trichobothria and Eb_3 is more distal to *Dt*.

The movable finger dentition is another novel character included in the species-keys table by Kovařík et al. (2020). Four types of denticles were considered: inner denticles (ID), inner accessory denticles (IAD), median denticles (MD) and outer denticles (OD). This quantitative character is included in Table 2 as additional information with data directly taken from Kovařík et al. (2020: 128–129, table 9). Since most of the data are missing, it is impossible to evaluate its applicability in distinguishing Yunnan *Scorpiops*.

Figures 186–200: *S. validus*, males under UV light. Figures 186–195. Pedipalp chela in dorsal (186–190) and dorsoexternal (191–195) views. Figures 196–200. Pectines.

Figures 201–215: *S. validus*, females under UV light. **Figures 201–210.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal (201–205) and dorsoexternal (206–210) views. **Figures 211–215.** Pectines.

Figures 216–219. *S. validus*, finger lobe development of an immature female (216); left pedipalp patella of a male showing a reduced ventral trichobothrium (217); comparison between two males (218–219).

Figures 220–225: *S. zhangshuyuani*, under UV light. **Figures 220–221, 224.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal (220) and dorsoexternal (221) and pectines (224) of male. **Figures 222–223, 225.** Pedipalp chela in dorsal (222) and dorsoexternal (223) and pectines (225) of female.

Figures 226–229: *Scorpiops* sp., male from Jinghong, Yunnan. Figures 226–228. Pedipalp chela in dorsal (226) and dorsoexternal (227), and pectines (228) under UV light. Figure 229. In vivo habitus.

Figures 230–235: Carapace (230, 233), tergites (231, 234) and telson (232, 235) of *S. kubani*, under UV light. Figures 230–232. Female. Figures 233–235. Male.

Finally, four types of pectine morphology were defined and assumed to be stable at the species level. However, data of several species are absent in this aspect (*S. puerensis*, *S. xui*, *S. yangi* and *S. zhangshuyuani*). *S. kubani* fits with the second type (P2): pectines with marginal lamellae I (basal) and III present, marginal lamella II not delimited, but connected with middle lamella forming a single compact unit; although marginal lamellae III is always developed, marginal lamellae I may be only indicated. *S. jendeki* accords with the third type (P3): pectines with two marginal and 1–4 middle lamellae present. *S. shidian* and *S. vachoni* (including *S. validus*) fall into the fourth type (P4): pectines with 3 marginal and 1–5 middle lamellae present. As for the four species with data absent from table 9 in Kovařík et al. (2020), the present study recapitulates the information from the original description: (1) the pectines of female *S. puerensis* were illustrated as having 3 marginal lamellae while that of the male have only 2 (Di et al., 2010b: 56, figs 12, 14); (2) the pectines of female *S. xui* were illustrated as having 2 marginal lamellae while that of the male have 3 (Sun & Zhu, 2010: 64, figs 4–5); (3) both sexes of *S. yangi* were illustrated as having 3 marginal lamellae (Zhu et al., 2007: 23, fig 6, 13); (4) neither detailed description nor explicit illustration were provided for *S. zhangshuyuani* (Ythier, 2019: 191, fig 2). However, these can only be determined by examining the type specimens.

Supplementary data for several species based on presumed topotypes

As already discussed in Tang (2022c), three *Scorpiops* species appear to be enigmatic due to their highly similar morphology, the members of the *S. vachoni* complex (as defined above). *Scorpiops validus* (Di et al., 2010) was synonymized with *S. vachoni* (Qi et al., 2005) by Kovařík et al. (2020) since several characters of both species overlap with each other (e.g., total length, number of ventral and external patellar trichobothria, and PTC). However, the authentic L/W ratio of pedipalp chela of *S. vachoni* is unknown; the morphometric values of *S. puerensis* also overlap with that of *S. validus*, except for this ratio. In the third chela group as defined above, *S. kubani* is also very similar to the *S. vachoni* complex in terms of the morphometric values (Table 2), but this species appears to be consistently smaller. Therefore, new morphometric data are hereby provided for the *S. vachoni* complex, based on the recently collected topotypes of these three species, as well as another three species, *S. kubani*, *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuani* (Table 3). The localities of these specimens are presented in Fig. 274, and these specimens are presumed to be conspecific with their most closely distributed species (the new species described in the present paper has demonstrated that congeners of *Scorpiops* in Yunnan can occur in extreme proximity). The L/W ratio calculated in this study is very different from the previous papers, probably due to the different methods. As a result, these data only convey the ratiometric difference between species, but do not replace the previous data. The number of different finger denticles

(IAD, MD, ID and OD) does not have to be accurate because some denticles may be interlaced, or some are either weakly developed or fused, and sometimes there is no clear separation between those denticle types (especially at the proximal end of the finger lobe, where OD, MD and ID may be mixed together); however, the slight deviation of counts ($\pm 1\text{--}3$) does not influence the general numerical trend presented in these species. Sample size may also influence the maximal/minimal value. Definition of these denticles is captioned in Figs. 266–271.

It is obvious from the photographs of the type specimens of *S. puerensis* and *S. validus* that both species exhibit two mutually distinct dorsal profiles in the chela shape (Di et al., 2011b: 13, figs 33, 37; 23, figs 77, 81). In qualitative terms, the dorsal chela shape of *S. puerensis* appears oval, while that of *S. validus* appears rectangular. This dorsal profile is delimited by the external carina and dorsal internal carina; thus, in *S. puerensis*, the distance between the two carinae increases progressively towards the proximal end, while in *S. validus*, the two carinae are essentially parallel. Therefore, the L/W ratio of *S. validus* has been recorded as higher than that of *S. puerensis*. If so, then *S. vachoni* appears to be more similar to *S. puerensis* than to *S. validus* (Qi et al., 2005: 19–20, figs 62–63).

S. kubani distributes closely to *S. puerensis* and *S. vachoni* in Yunnan and also exhibits an analogous overall morphology with the *S. vachoni* complex: coloration essentially brownish black, proximal lobe of the pedipalp movable finger pronounced in males, chela moderately elongate (between *S. jendeki* and *S. shidian*) and similar number of ventral and external patellar trichobothria and PTC. However, based on the previous information, this species can be separated from *S. vachoni* complex by the following characters: proximal lobe of the pedipalp movable finger weaker in females (vs. comparatively stronger in females of *S. vachoni* complex) (cf. Di et al., 2011b: 7, figs. 19, 21; 13, figs 38, 40; 23, figs 82, 84), a different position of trichobothrium Eb_3 on the pedipalp chela manus (C vs. A), and a different morphology of pectine (P2 vs. P4). It is important to note that, the locality of *S. kubani* in Yunnan was not included in their distributional map in Kovařík et al. (2020), although they listed “China” as one of the countries where *S. kubani* occurs in the table below (Kovařík et al., 2020: 127, fig 799). Additionally, one unidentified adult male *Scorpiops* sp. was found in Mt. Jinuo, Jinghong City (Fig. 226–229), which is located between the locality of *S. kubani* and *S. vachoni* in Yunnan.

Below summarizes the results of the observation on the 6 species studied (Table 3), but also associates with the previous data as shown in Table 2.

(1) Total length

All the species examined yielded a similar morphometric value for this parameter. However, *S. kubani* was found to be consistently smaller than the three species of the *S. vachoni* complex with minor overlap. In a small male *S. kubani*, no hemispermatothores were retrieved, and it was

initially presumed to be a subadult (Fig. 86). However, the proximal lobe of this individual clearly indicates that it is an adult (Fig. 52). In another even smaller male (Fig. 87), hemispermatophores were successfully found and its proximal lobe is also pronounced (Fig. 53). Therefore, the former small male may have recently performed a courtship in nature, and its hemispermatophore failed to regenerate when it was still alive. Two size classes of adult males have been previously reported in another species of Chactoida Pocock, 1893 by Benton (1991), *Tetratrichobothrius flavicaudis* (DeGeer, 1778). The two size classes found in *S. kubani* here show not only the disparity in total length, but also the difference in the robustness of pedipalp and the size of telson vesicle (Figs. 86–88). This dichotomous size variation is also found in adult female *S. kubani*, demonstrated by the presence of embryos (Fig. 89–90), as well as in males of *S. vachoni* (Fig. 184–185) and *S. validus* (Fig. 218–219).

(2) Finger lobe development

Inconsistent with the previous result in Kovařík et al. (2020), females of *S. vachoni* do not have a relatively pronounced lobe (undulate), but this is present in the remaining species and sexes of *S. vachoni* complex, especially in males. The prominence of this lobe may correlate with sexual maturity in males. Qualitatively, a pronounced lobe is only found in mature males (e.g., Figs. 97–101), although the minimal size is unknown, hindering a reliable maturity determination by this character alone (as a relatively pronounced lobe is found in some subadult buthids; e.g., *Olivierus* sp., Tang pers. obs.). Females of the *S. vachoni* complex exhibit weaker lobes than the males, but only those of *S. puerensis* and *S. validus* are still stronger than those of the remaining species studied (females), i.e., *S. kubani*, *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuanii*. The degree of development of the lobe in female *S. vachoni* is stronger than in female *S. kubani* but weaker than in the other two species of the *S. vachoni* complex. In *S. kubani*, the prominence of lobe in males is similar to or greater than in the females of the *S. vachoni* complex. Both males and females of *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuanii* possess weaker lobes than *S. kubani*, leaving a negligible proximal gap when closed, and the male *S. shidian* barely approximates the female *S. kubani* in lobe size. The L/D ratio of the finger lobe is recorded for *S. kubani*, the species of *S. vachoni* complex and the unidentified *Scorpiops* from Jinghong (Table 3), but these quantified data are only referential for conveying the interspecific difference. Measurement is shown in Figs. 272–273.

(3) Pedipalp movable finger dentition

Significant variation range was found in IAD and MD among conspecifics (numerical disparity ca. 10–20). Among all the species, *S. vachoni* shows the highest maximum value for IAD (80) and MD (116). The high value recorded for finger dentition is successively presented in another two species, *S. validus* and *S. zhangshuyuanii*. *S. validus* also shows a high value of MD and one juvenile female had been recorded with 103 and 109 MD on each movable finger, while the remaining

species conspicuously overlap with each other (ca. 75–95 for MD and ca. 45–70 for IAD). A rather high count for MD (91–100) and IAD (70–73) is exhibited in *S. zhangshuyuanii* as well. The high count for MD in *S. validus* results from a secondary proliferation of denticles at the proximal part and a more elongate pedipalp and this is also present in some *S. vachoni*. It is worth noting that the sample sizes for *S. vachoni*, *S. zhangshuyuanii* and *S. validus* were not the same, so the variation range of *S. zhangshuyuanii* is only referential. As for ID and OD, all the species overlap with each other in the number of ID (ca. 4–8), but there is a general tendency of consistency in some species (i.e., no significant variation range). Only one male *S. vachoni* had been recorded to have 6 ID on its right pedipalp, while most were 7 and some were 8. Within the *S. vachoni* complex, *S. puerensis* and *S. validus* consistently revealed the lowest numerical range for OD (9–14), which distinguishes them from the most closely related *S. kubani* (in terms of the overall morphology). This number is higher in *S. vachoni* and only one male was recorded to have 13 OD (most, or 10/16 fingers had 15). A case of 12 OD was found in a female *S. kubani* but discounted due to the injury on its finger that obscured the dentition, although the spacing between each remaining pair of adjacent OD is normal; an anomaly was also discovered in the right pedipalp movable finger of an adult male *S. kubani* (Fig. 85), as well as in the left movable finger of an adult male *S. vachoni* (Fig. 182). Extraordinary values for MD and OD recorded in the right pedipalp of an adult male *S. shidian* are isolated in parentheses of Table 3. The ID on the right pedipalp of that individual was also arranged in a peculiar pattern: 4/6 of which clustered at the distal tip of movable finger, between the first IAD and the distal denticle.

(4) Pedipalp chela L/W ratio

As clarified above, the ratios calculated in this study only convey the differences between species. The ratio variation range of the same species can be different if it was measured by different authors. To avoid such ambiguity, photographs of pedipalp chelae of all adult specimens examined here are included for reference. Chela shape varied within the same species, which to some extent obscured interspecific differences. However, as roughly categorized above, *S. kubani*, *S. puerensis*, *S. vachoni* and *S. validus* fall into a group with elongate but robust chelae, while *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuanii* fall into the group with elongate but slender chelae. With *S. vachoni* excluded (the authentic L/W ratio value of this species remains unknown), although there may be differences in the method of measuring the ratio, the general trend for *S. kubani*, *S. puerensis* and *S. validus* presented here is consistent with the previous studies (cf. Tables 2 and 3), i.e., among these three species, *S. validus* tends to have the most slender chela while *S. puerensis* has the most stout one. Contrary to the assumption based on the original illustration of *S. vachoni* in the previous paragraph, the ratio of the chela in this species is intermediate between *S. puerensis* and *S. validus*, but closer to the latter. However,

Figures 236–241: Carapace (236, 239), tergites (237, 240) and telson (238, 240) of *S. puerensis*, under UV light. Figures 236–238. Female. Figures 239–240. Male.

the shape indeed resembles that of *S. puerensis* (i.e., the maximal width of the chelal manus is more proximal, while in *S. validus* it is more mesial). Therefore, L/W ratio alone may not be sufficient to describe the morphology of the pedipalp chela. Females of *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuani* are similar to each other in this aspect, but the latter has relatively narrower chelae. The two species may also be distinguished by a higher finger denticle count in the latter. The difference between the males of these two species is even more prominent and male *S. zhangshuyuani* represents the one *Scorpiops* species that exhibits the highest L/W ratio of the pedipalp chela in Yunnan Province.

(5) Pedipalp patellar trichobothria number

Substantial interspecific overlap is found in either ventral or external trichobothria numbers on the pedipalp patella. Although there was overlap across species, the ventral trichobothria of *S. shidian* consistently showed the maximum value (13 trichobothria) and most specimens of *S. shidian* were found to have 12 trichobothria, while in *S. kubani* and the *S. vachoni* complex, it was often 10 and never exceeded 11; 8 trichobothria was only recorded once in the left pedipalp patella of a juvenile male in *S. vachoni* (Fig. 183), while 36/42 of the examined patellae had 10 and 5/42 had 11. The higher count discovered in *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuani* may be correlated with their extremely elongated pedipalps. The external trichobothria, however, do not show any specific consistency or significant disparity. The lowest (17 trichobothria) and highest (20 trichobothria) values of *S. kubani* were recorded only once, but this may be abnormal. In a female of *S. kubani*, only 16 external trichobothria were observed on the left pedipalp patella. However, this isolated case was discounted because part of the integument was damaged, preventing a reliable count of the trichobothria. Similarly, 17 trichobothria were observed in only one adult female *S. validus*, on its right pedipalp, and only two *S. vachoni* had 17 trichobothria. In conclusion, within the species investigated in this study, only the ventral trichobothrial counts may be informative for differential diagnoses. It is also interesting to note a reduced ventral trichobothrium observed on the left pedipalp of an adult male *S. validus* (Fig. 217, above).

(6) Pectinal teeth count (PTC)

This discrete character greatly overlaps interspecifically because most *Scorpiops* species possess short pectines with low numbers of teeth, which excludes the possibility of showing obvious numerical disparity as observed in some Old World buthids. Hence, this character cannot be used for distinguishing the six species studied herein. However, the highest value (9 teeth) was only recorded in the males of *S. vachoni* (3/32 pectines) and *S. zhangshuyuani* (2/2 pectines). Furthermore, female of *S. zhangshuyuani* possesses proportionally sharper and thinner pectinal teeth. Interestingly, fusion (or incomplete separation) of adjacent pectinal teeth has been found multiple times across different species.

(7) Fulcra

Fulcra were observed in all the species examined. The presence of fulcra in *S. kubani* and *S. vachoni* contradicts the diagnostic table in Kovařík et al. (2020). The fulcra are often more developed in males of larger species, like members of the *S. vachoni* complex.

(8) Pectine morphology

The lamellar division was found to be rather unstable within conspecifics, even in the same individual. For example, in *S. shidian*, all four types of pectine morphology are present (P1: Fig. 154, right pectine; P2: Fig. 152, right pectine; P3: Fig. 153, right pectine; P4: Fig. 130, both pectines). Furrows that delimit the marginal lamellae and median lamellae, or each marginal lamella, may not be complete. The median lamella either has evident furrows or forms a compact piece. As a result, this character is excluded from the supplementary data table. However, in males of *S. puerensis* and both sexes of *S. vachoni* and *S. validus*, the three marginal lamellae are often defined, with II and III sometimes partially incomplete.

Based on the current investigation, consistent morphological differences were found between *S. vachoni* and *S. validus*: (1) the proximal lobe on the dorsal edge of pedipalp movable finger is stronger in *S. validus*, and this disparity is greater between the females of the two species; (2) a more slender pedipalp in *S. validus* (somewhat overlapped between the two species); (3) higher maximum counts for all four types of finger dentition in *S. vachoni*, especially the IAD and MD; (4) ventral trichobothrial counts of the pedipalp patella never below 10 in *S. vachoni*; (5) a slightly higher PTC in *S. vachoni* (never below 7), while lower in *S. validus* (never exceeding 8). Therefore, *S. validus* is hereby restored from its synonymy with *S. vachoni*. However, no evidence was found to support the previous diagnostic description regarding the shape of pedipalp chela from the lateral aspect (i.e., rounded in *S. vachoni* but flattened in *S. validus*), thus this cannot be used as a differential character.

Discussion

The present study investigated eight morphological characters that were applied in the differential diagnoses in the previous papers for six *Scorpiops* species from Yunnan Province, China. The results are generally consistent with the previous ones (e.g., total length, patellar trichobothria number and PTC), while some showed contradictions.

The most crucial contradiction lies in the pectine morphology, which revealed inconsistency within the same species or even in the same individual. It is not feasible to unambiguously classify all the studied species into the four pectine types defined by Kovařík et al. (2020). Furthermore, two characters of the Yunnan population of *S. kubani* conflicted with those given in Kovařík et al. (2020: 128, table 9). The first contradictory character is the number of OD on the pedipalp movable finger. The present study examined seven males

Figures 242–247: Carapace (242, 245), tergites (243, 246) and telson (244, 247) of *S. shidian*, under UV light. Figures 242–244. Female. Figures 245–247. Male.

Figures 248–253: Carapace (248, 251), tergites (249, 252) and telson (250, 253) of *S. vachoni*, under UV light. **Figures 248–250.** Female. **Figures 251–253.** Male.

Figures 254–259: Carapace (254, 257), tergites (255, 258) and telson (256, 259) of *S. validus*, under UV light. Figures 254–256. Female. Figures 257–259. Male.

Figures 260–265: Carapace, tergites and telson of *S. zhangshuyuani*, under UV light. Figures 204–206. Female. Figures 207–209. Male.

Figures 266–271: Examples of definition of pedipalp finger dentation for studied congeners of *Scorpiops tongtongi* sp. n. in Yunnan (IAD = yellow, MD = green, ID = blue, OD = red). **Figure 266.** Right movable finger of a female *S. kubani*, showing a clear and normal arrangement of dentation. **Figure 267.** Left movable finger of a female *S. puerensis*, showing subjective separation of MD and IAD (see text). **Figure 268.** Right movable finger of a female *S. shidian* (purple arrows: several abraded MD; pink arrow: an extra denticle between MD and IAD). **Figure 269.** Left movable finger of a female *S. vachoni*, showing four extra denticles flanking IAD (red arrows, considered as IAD). **Figure 270.** Left movable finger of a female *S. validus*, showing a secondary proliferation at proximal part (more than one row of denticle). **Figure 271.** Left movable finger of a female *S. zhangshuyuani*, showing a high value of MD number.

Diagnostic characters	<i>S. jendeki</i> 詹氏类蝎	" <i>S. kubani</i> " 库氏类蝎	<i>S. puerensis</i> 普洱类蝎	<i>S. shidian</i> 施甸类蝎	<i>S. vachoni</i> 瓦氏类蝎
Total length ♂/♀ (mm)	25–32.2/42.1	44–48/44–48	48.8–57.1/60	47–60/45–59.81	52.89/42.28
Finger lobe development ♂/♀	0/0	1/0	1/1	0/0	1/1
IAD	ca. 10	ca. 50	?	ca. 60	?
MD	ca. 50	ca. 70	?	ca. 80	?
ID/OD	5/9	4–5/11–13	5–6/12–13	6/13–15	6/11–13
Pedipalp L/W ratio ♂/♀	2.1~2.3/2.1~2.4	2.9~3.2/2.7~3.2	2.6~2.8/2.6~2.8	3.3~3.5/3.2~3.5	1.46*/1.92*
nVt of patella ♂/♀	6~7/6~7	9~10/9~11	10~11/10~11	10~12/10~12	10/10
nEt of patella ♂/♀	17/17	18/17~18	18/18	17~18/17~18	17~18/17~18
<i>Eb</i> ₃ pos. (Kovařík et al., 2020)	D	C	A	A	A
Pectine (Kovařík et al., 2020)	P3	P2	?	P4	P4
PTC ♂/♀	4~5/4~5	6~8/6~7	7~8/7~8	7~8/6~8	7~8/7
Fulcra	×	×	√	√	×
Telson L/H ratio ♂/♀	2.7/2.9	3.5/3.8	3.7/3.0	3.4~3.5/2.8~2.9	3.1/?
Specimens studied by authors	8♀ 1J♂	3♂4♀ 2J♂4J♀	3♂4♀ 2J♂1J♀	5♂5♀ 1J♂	1♂1♀
Origin in Yunnan	保山 Baoshan	勐海 Menghai	普洱 Puer	施甸 Shidian	勐腊 Mengla

Diagnostic characters	<i>S. validus</i> 强壮类蝎	<i>S. xui</i> 徐氏类蝎	<i>S. yangi</i> 杨氏类蝎	<i>S. zhangshuyuanii</i> 张氏类蝎	<i>S. tongtongi</i> sp. n. 通氏类蝎
Total length ♂/♀ (mm)	50–59.8/50–58	54.1–56/58–66	46.1–47.8/51.3	?/49.1–51.3	?/41.9
Finger lobe development ♂/♀	1/1	0/0	0/0	?/0	?/0
IAD	?	?	?	?	ca. 45–47
MD	?	?	?	?	ca. 86–88
ID/OD	?/6/11–13	6/13	?	?	4/11
Pedipalp L/W ratio ♂/♀	2.94~3.16/2.93~3.16	4.0~4.1/3.4~3.6	3.4/3.3	4.7~5.4/4.2~4.3	?/2.85
nVt of patella ♂/♀	9~10/8~11	10/10	9~10/9~10	?/11	?/7
nEt of patella ♂/♀	17~18/17~18	18~19/18~19	18/18	?/18	?/17
<i>Eb</i> ₃ pos. (Kovařík et al., 2020)	?A	A	A	A/C	C
Pectine (Kovařík et al., 2020)	?P4	?	?	?	P1
PTC ♂/♀	6~8/6~6	8/7	6~7/5~6	?/7~8	?/6
Fulcra	√	×	×	√	√
Telson L/H ratio ♂/♀	3.6/3.3	3.3/3.6	3/3.4	?/3.5	?/2.8
Specimens studied by authors	5♂5♀	2♂2♀	4♂1♀	2♂2♀	1♀
Origin in Yunnan	红河 Honghe	孟连 Menglian	马关 Maguan	盈江 Yingjiang	盈江 Yingjiang

Table 2. Morphological comparison of *Scorpiops* species in Yunnan with diagnostic characters cited or calculated only from the previous papers and the new species described in this study (excluding coloration); for the categories defined for the trichobothrial position and pectine morphology, refer to the text or Kovařík et al. (2020). 0 = weak to absent, 1 = moderate to prominent. √ = present, × = absent. J = Juvenile. *Erroneous data from original description. Note that the data of finger dentation, trichobothria position, pectinal fulcra, and telson L/D ratio for *S. kubani* are taken from Kovařík et al. (2020), based on the type specimens from Laos, while the remaining ones are from Di et al. (2011b).

and eight females, which yielded a variation range of 14–16, completely partitioned from the previous range of 11–13. The second character is the presence/absence of pectinal fulcra. All 15 specimens showed the presence of fulcra under UV light, although in some individuals, several fulcra were smaller in size. This character is also vaguely visible in Di et al. (2010b: 59, fig. 36). One may have a different opinion on the degree of development of these small structures, and consider them to be “reduced to absent”. However, by comparing them with the scorpion taxa that are explicitly defined by the absence

of fulcra, e.g., genus *Ananteris* Thorell, 1891 (cf. Lourenço, 2003: 185, fig. 7), these structures are obviously present in *S. kubani*, at least for the Yunnan population. All of these contradictions weakened the separation of *S. kubani* from the *S. vachoni* complex defined herein. However, species complexes or groups are often designated subjectively, without standard criteria. Excluding the position of trichobothria *Eb*₃ on the pedipalp chela manus, only the proximal lobe on the movable finger of the pedipalp can potentially distinguish these species (i.e., female *S. kubani* possess weaker lobes than those of the

Diagnostic characters	<i>"S. kubani"</i> 库氏类蝎	<i>S. puerensis</i> 普洱类蝎	<i>S. shidian</i> 施甸类蝎	<i>S. vachoni</i> 瓦氏类蝎
Total length ♂/♀ (mm)	39.9–45.3/40.2–46.7	46.2–49.8/51.6–54.4	45.7–51.7/45.8–52.4	47.2–54.0/48.1–54.8
Finger lobe development ♂/♀	1/0	1/1	0/0	1/0
Finger lobe L/D ratio ♂/♀	3.50–5.33/6.09–10.0	2.90–3.44/4.61–5.16		3.18–4.16/5.37–7.14
IAD	ca. 45–59	ca. 47–51	ca. 44–67	ca. 53–80
MD	ca. 76–88	ca. 80–92	ca. (69)77–95	ca. 92–116
ID/OD	4–8/14–16	4–6/9–14	6–7/(10)14–16	(6)7–8/13–15
Pedipalp L/W ratio ♂/♀	3.24–3.40/3.05–3.45	3.03–3.18/3.04–3.18	3.79–4.14/3.66–4.01	3.14–3.45/3.23–3.43
nVt of patella ♂/♀	9–10/8–10	8–11/10–11	12–13/11–13	(8)10–11/10–11
nEt of patella ♂/♀	(17)18–19(20)/18–19	18–19/17–19	18–20/17–18	17–18/18–18
PTC ♂/♀	7–8/6–7	7–8/6–8	7–8/7–8	7–9/7–8
Fulcra	√	√	√	√
Specimens studied	7♂8♀	5♂5♀	4♂7♀ 2J♂1J♀	5♂3♀ 11J♂2J♀
Origin in Yunnan	勐海 Menghai	普洱 Puer	施甸 Shidian	勐腊 Mengla

Diagnostic characters	<i>S. validus</i> 强壮类蝎	<i>S. zhangshuyuani</i> 张氏类蝎	<i>S. sp.</i> 类蝎属未定种
Total length ♂/♀ (mm)	43.1–54.3/46.2–52.8	42.6/53.8	44.0/?
Finger lobe development ♂/♀	1/1	0/0	1/?
Finger lobe L/D ratio ♂/♀	2.70–3.62/4.11–5.20		3.66/?
IAD	ca. 44–58	ca. 70–73	ca. 55–58
MD	ca. 88–109	ca. 91–100	ca. 87
ID/OD	5–8/11–14	5–7/13–15	7–8/15
Pedipalp L/W ratio ♂/♀	3.32–3.63/3.38–3.61	5.22/4.11	3.25/?
nVt of patella ♂/♀	9–10/9–11	11–12/11	10–11/?
nEt of patella ♂/♀	18–19/17–19	18/18	18/?
PTC ♂/♀	7–8/6–7	9/8	7/?
Fulcra	√	√	√
Specimens studied	5♂5♀ 1J♀	1♂1♀	1♂
Origin in Yunnan	红河 Honghe	盈江 Yingjiang	景洪 Jinghong

Table 3. Supplementary morphometric values for *Scorpiops kubani*, *S. puerensis*, *S. shidian*, *S. vachoni*, *S. validus* and *S. zhangshuyuani* based on recently collected specimens.

S. vachoni complex). The pronounced lobe present in males of *S. kubani* prevents its reliable separation from the males of the *S. vachoni* complex. Nevertheless, it is highly possible that the Yunnan population of *S. kubani* represents another new species, separated by the Lancang River from the Laos population that occurs far away, with *S. vachoni* distributed in between.

Total length was a character with utility in distinguishing *S. kubani* from the three species of the *S. vachoni* complex. Individuals of *S. kubani* were generally smaller in length with minor overlap. The remaining two species (i.e., *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuani*) have an intermediate variation range compared to those four species, but they can be readily identified by other characters (e.g., pedipalp morphology).

The trichobothrial numbers of the pedipalp patella and PTC proved to be of limited use in differentiating the six Yunnan *Scorpiops* species. The ranges of variation of the external trichobothrial numbers of the pedipalp patella of these species overlap with each other significantly, and are unreliable for differential diagnosis. Higher ventral trichobothrial numbers of the pedipalp patella are present in two species with markedly elongate pedipalps (*S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuani*), and that of PTC is present in *S. vachoni* and *S. zhangshuyuani*. However, certain species showed limited variation in these characters, which can separate them from other species (i.e., the numerical count of a certain character never exceeds or is lower than a maximum/minimum value). Nevertheless, due to the fact that the overlap is often present, large sample sizes are required when identifying a set of

Figures 272–273: Measuring method used for development degree of finger proximal lobe (external view of pedipalp fingers). **Figure 272.** Male *S. validus*. **Figure 273.** Female *S. kubani*.

specimens from the same locality, unless the count for these individuals segregated at the extremum of a certain species and can be distinguished from the others.

Issues regarding movable finger dentition are complicated. To begin with, the definition and separation of these denticles are subjective, except that ID and OD are normally distinct (in

a few scenarios, however, these two denticles are positioned closely to and similar to other denticles in size, especially at the proximal part). These finger dentitions are defined by Soleglad & Sissom (2001), and three basic denticle types are explicit: median denticles (MD), inner denticles (ID) and outer denticles (OD). However, the authors did not mention

Figure 274: Map showing known *Scorpiops* species in Yunnan (only cited from previous papers: *S. jendeki* (●), *S. kubani* (●), *S. puerensis* (●), *S. shidian* (●), *S. vachoni* (●), *S. validus* (●), *S. xui* (●), *S. yangi* (●), *S. zhangshuyuani* (●), *S. sp.* (●) and *S. tongtongi* sp. n. (★). Presumed topotypes of species and Yunnan population of *S. kubani* examined in this study are plotted as ○ (next to closest colored symbols).

how to separate the inner accessory denticles (IAD) from MD at the proximity: “...in particular the euscorpids, these accessory denticles are constant in their overall occurrence and in some cases exist in such numbers as to form secondary denticle rows approaching the median denticle row in overall denticle density...”. In the new species described herein, IAD do not evidently partition from MD when they approach the proximal part of the finger, and random series of denticles continue the entire length of fingers dorsal edge. As a result, IAD is separated from MD subjectively: no more IAD were considered after the most proximal OD, and the final (most proximal) IAD is at the same level as that of the OD (Figs. 21–22). However, in the other six congeners studied (previously all included in *Euscorpids*), the two rows are usually more defined. Nevertheless, it still becomes ambiguous when these two denticles are mixed with each other at the proximity. Spacing between adjacent denticles is a primary parameter in distinguishing the denticles. For example, in Fig. 266, the three denticles indicated by three corresponding arrows have two distinct spacings, and the bottom one was then considered to be an offset MD. Another important consideration is to ensure the continuity of MD. In Fig. 267, one denticle is positioned closely to the most proximal OD, and considered as an MD. Although the purple line seems to be a more reasonable denticle series due to its more linear arrangement, it begins from the IAD distally and IAD is considered accessory. As a result, the pink line is chosen to be the main series, ensuring the continuity of MD towards the proximity. Apart from the subjective separation of IAD and MD at the proximal finger, other problems may also obstruct the counting of denticles. For instance, in Fig. 268, several MD were abraded (purple

arrows) and an extra denticle is present between IAD and MD (pink arrow). In a more intricate scenario, an anomaly of denticle arrangement was observed in the right pedipalp movable finger of a male *S. kubani* (Fig. 85) and the left movable finger of an adult male *S. vachoni* (Fig. 182). The distal series of denticles do not form any clear rows, preventing the independent counting of IAD and MD. Given that the separation of IAD and MD could be subjective due to their interlaced arrangement, accurate counting may not be possible or important; or, the two types of denticles should be otherwise enumerated together. The present study obtained a similar variation range from half of the studied species, leaving *S. vachoni*, *S. validus* and *S. zhangshuyuani* as three species that exhibited the highest value. Counts for *S. shidian* were slightly higher than *S. kubani* and *S. puerensis* due to its more slender pedipalp chela. The problem of the utility of the dentition number is similar to the trichobothrial number and PTC discussed above. The overlap is present interspecifically and the disparity may only be revealed after examining sufficient number of specimens.

The remaining two characters are the pedipalp chela L/W ratio and the finger lobe development. In this study, the finger lobe development of four species is further tentatively quantified by the L/D ratio. However, ratiometric values can always be influenced by slight deviations and subjective considerations if they are manually measured and may not be consistent among different authors. Thus, an extremely precise calculation should not be a prerequisite for identifying species, but authors should stipulate their measurement method by giving illustrations for the subsequent investigators to reproduce. On the other hand, ratiometric values regarding the chela shape do have a function

in quantitatively comparing different species, but the overlap present in some different species curtails its utility (e.g., *S. vachoni* and *S. validus* are similar in this aspect). As for the finger lobe development, explicit measurement is also difficult to implement because the dorsal edge of movable finger itself is a curve, and decisions about the opposite ends of the horizontal line (e.g., Figs. 272–273, red lines) when measuring the length of the lobe can be variable. The depth is measured thereafter, by adjusting the vertical measuring line (e.g., Figs. 272–273, yellow lines) perpendicular to the horizontal one. Therefore, the depth measurement is dependent on the length measurement. Hence, adequate sample size is again required to reduce the variance arising from slight errors caused by manual measurement.

In conclusion, the identification of *Scorpiops* species in Yunnan based solely on external morphology could prove difficult in most species due to their highly overlapping morphometrics (hemispermatophores and karyotypes were not investigated in this study). Therefore, accurate localities and large sample sizes of the specimens are essential for achieving a more reliable identification.

Acknowledgements

I am very grateful to Dr. Graeme Lowe for the photo stacking work and valuable comments on the manuscript, as well as for his constant kind help in many ways. I would like to thank Tongtong (通通) for his provision of the holotype and a pair of adult *Scorpiops zhangshuyuani*. My thankfulness also goes to five collectors who provided the specimens of five *Scorpiops* species: 邱航 (*S. kubani*), 何进平 (*S. puerensis*), 杨国皓 (*S. shidian*), 贾清权 (*S. vachoni*), and an anonymous collector (*S. validus*). Finally, I thank Professor Victor Fet and František Kovařík for their review.

References

- BENTON, T. G. 1991. The life history of *Euscorpium flavicaudis* (Scorpiones, Chactidae). *The Journal of Arachnology*, 43: 105–110.
- DI, Z.-Y., Z.-J. CAO, Y.-L. WU & W.-X. LI. 2010a. A new species of the genus *Euscorpium* Vachon, 1980 (Scorpiones: Euscorpidae, Scorpiopinae) from Yunnan, China. *Zootaxa*, 2361: 13–22.
- DI, Z.-Y., Y.-W. HE, Z.-J. CAO, Y.-L. WU, & W.-X. LI. 2011a. The first record of the family Euscorpidae (Arachnida: Scorpiones) from Central China, with a key of Chinese species of the genus *Scorpiops*. *Euscorpium*, 118: 1–9.
- DI, Z.-Y., Y.-W. HE, Y.-L. WU, Z.-J. CAO, H. LIU, D.-H. JIANG & W.-X. LI. 2011b. The scorpions of Yunnan (China): updated identification key, new record and redescription of *Euscorpium kubani* and *E. shidian* (Arachnida, Scorpiones). *ZooKeys*, 82: 1–33.
- DI, Z.-Y., Y.-L. WU, Z.-J. CAO, H. XIAO & W.-X. LI. 2010b. A catalogue of the genus *Euscorpium* Vachon, 1980 (Scorpiones: Euscorpidae, Scorpiopinae) from China, with description of a new species. *Zootaxa*, 2477: 49–61.
- DI, Z.-Y., X.-B. XU, Z.-J. CAO, Y.-L. WU & W.-X. LI. 2013. Notes on the scorpions (Arachnida, Scorpiones) from Xizang with the redescription of *Scorpiops jendeki* Kovařík, 2000 (Scorpiones, Euscorpidae) from Yunnan (China). *ZooKeys*, 301: 51–99.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 1994. *Scorpiops irenae* sp. n. from Nepal and *Scorpiops hardwickei jendeki* subsp. n. from Yunnan, China (Arachnida: Scorpionida: Vaejovidae). *Acta Societatis Zoologicae Bohemicae*, 58: 61–66.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 2005. Three new species of the genera *Euscorpium* Vachon, 1980 and *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 from Asia (Scorpiones: Euscorpidae, Scorpiopinae). *Euscorpium*, 27: 1–10.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 2009. *Illustrated catalog of scorpions. Part I. Introductory remarks; keys to families and genera; subfamily Scorpioninae with keys to Heterometrus and Pandinus species*. Prague: Clairon Production, 170 pp.
- KOVAŘÍK, F & A. A. OJANGUREN AFFILASTRO. 2013. *Illustrated catalog of scorpions. Part II. Bothriuridae; Chaerilidae; Buthidae I, genera Compsobuthus, Hottentotta, Isometrus, Lychas, and Sassanidotus*. Prague: Clairon Production, 400 pp.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE, M. STOCKMANN & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2020. Revision of genus-group taxa in the family Scorpiopidae Kraepelin, 1905, with description of 15 new species (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Euscorpium*, 325: 1–142.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. 2003. The genus *Ananteris* Thorell (Scorpiones, Buthidae) in French Guyana. *Revista Ibérica de Aracnología*, 7: 183–188.
- LV, H.-Y & Z.-Y. DI. 2022. The first record of *Scorpiops bhutanensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 from China, with the first report of its female (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae). *Euscorpium*, 358: 1–8.
- QI, J.-X., M.-S. ZHU & W. R. LOURENÇO. 2005. Eight new species of the genera *Scorpiops* Peters, *Euscorpium* Vachon, and *Chaerilus* Simon (Scorpiones: Euscorpidae, Chaerilidae) from Tibet and Yunnan, China. *Euscorpium*, 32: 1–40.
- STAHNKE, H. L. 1971. Scorpion nomenclature and mensuration. *Entomological News*, 81: 297–316.

- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & V. FET. 2003a. The scorpion sternum: structure and phylogeny (Scorpiones: Orthosterni). *Euscorpius*, 5: 1–34.
- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & V. FET. 2003b. High-level systematics and phylogeny of the extant scorpions (Scorpiones: Orthosterni). *Euscorpius*, 11: 1–175.
- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & W. D. SISSOM, 2001. Phylogeny of the family Euscorpiidae Laurie, 1896: a major revision. Pp. 25–111 in Fet, V. & P.A. Selden (eds). *Scorpions 2001. In memoriam Gary A. Polis*. Burnham Beeches, Bucks: British Arachnological Society.
- SUN, D. & M.-S. ZHU. 2010. One new species of scorpion belonging to the genus *Euscorpiops* Vachon, 1980 from Yunnan, China (Scorpiones: Euscorpiidae, Scorpiopinae). *Zootaxa*, 2399: 61–68.
- TANG, V. 2022a. A standardized list of scorpion names in Chinese, with an etymological approach. *Euscorpius*, 350: 1–91.
- TANG, V. 2022b. A new scorpion genus and species from China, *Qianxie solegladi* gen. et sp. n. (Scorpiones: Pseudochactidae). *Euscorpius*, 351: 1–19.
- TANG, V. 2022c. Scorpions of China: an updated checklist with comments on some taxonomic issues (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Euscorpius*, 355: 1–18.
- VACHON, M. 1974. Etude des caractères utilisés pour classer les familles et les genres de Scorpions (Arachnides). 1. La trichobothriotaxie en Arachnologie. Sigles trichobothriaux et types de trichobothriotaxie chez les scorpions. *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire naturelle, Paris*, (3), 140 (Zool. 104), mai-juin 1973: 857–958.
- YTHIER, E. 2019. A new species of *Euscorpiops* Vachon, 1980, from China (Scorpiones, Scorpiopidae). *Bulletin de la Société entomologique de France*, 124(2): 189–196.
- ZHU, M.-S., L. ZHANG & W. R. LOURENÇO. 2007. One new species of scorpion belonging to the genus *Euscorpiops* Vachon, 1980 from South China (Scorpiones: Euscorpiidae, Scorpiopinae). *Zootaxa*, 1582: 19–25.